

Short communication

First record of *Scorlupella montana* (Hem.: Fulgoroidea: Issidae) from Iran

F. Mozaffarian^{1&*} and V. M. Gnezdilov²

1. Insect Taxonomy Research Department, Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection, P.O. Box 1454, Tehran 19395, Iran, 2. Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Universitetskaya nab.1, 199034 St., Petersburg, Russia.

*Corresponding author, E-mail: mozaffarian@iripp.ir, faribamozaffarian@gmail.com

چکیده

در بررسی زنجبرک‌های خانواده‌ی Issidae در ایران، نمونه‌هایی متعلق به گونه‌ی *Scorlupella montana* (Becker) جمع‌آوری و شناسایی گردید که جنس و گونه‌ی آن اولین گزارش از ایران می‌باشد.

The family Issidae is one of the largest families of the Fulgoroidea that has worldwide distribution, with many species in arid regions of Western Palaearctic. The members of this family are usually subbrachypterous, with rounded or ovoid body shape.

Approximately 43 issid species have already been recorded from Iran (Dlabola, 1971, 1974, 1980, 1981, 1982; Behdad, 1988; Mirzayans, 1995; Abaii, 2000). Dlabola was in fact the main researcher on the Iranian issid fauna. He described 37 species, which is 86 percent of the fauna. At least three of them have been recorded as pests on almond and oaks (Abaii, 2000). Eleven species had been identified by Dr. J. Dlabola in 1970s and deposited in the Hayk Mirzayans Insect Museum (HMIM), Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection, Iran (Mirzayans, 1995).

During the collecting trips to North West of Iran in 2008, several females of *Scorlupella montana* (Becker) were collected in steppe, on *Austragallus* sp., at the altitudes of 1350-2645 m, close to the agricultural areas and grasslands. Additional material of the species could also be recognized from Golestan province in further studies among unidentified specimens in HMIM. This is the first report of the genus and species of *S. montana* from Iran.

Material examined – 1 ♀, Golestan, Golestan National Park, Khajenarenj, 1350 m, 4 May 1999, Leg.: Moghaddam / Barari / Manzari; 7 ♀, Golestan, Golestan National Park, Almeh, Karkoli, 1700 m, 13 June 2000, Leg.: Badii / Ebrahimi / Moghaddam / Mofidi-Neyestanak; 3 ♀, Azarbaijan-e Sharghi, Ajab Shir, Yaichi Vill., N: 37° 35' 27.2" E: 46° 11' 03.7", 1922 m, 15 June 2008, Leg.: Mozaffarian; 1 ♀, Azarbaijan-e Sharghi, Tabriz, Matnagh, 16 June 2008, Leg.: Mozaffarian; 1 ♀, Azarbaijan-e Sharghi, Heris, Tazeh Kand, N: 38° 16'

04.6" E: 47° 12' 14.9", 2078 m, 17 June 2008, Leg.: Mozaffarian; 1 ♀, Azarbaijan-e Sharghi, Kandovan, N: 37° 45' 45.8" E: 46° 17' 40.5", 2645 m, 18 June 2008, Leg.: Mozaffarian.

According to Emeljanov's nomenclature of areals (Emeljanov, 1974) *S. montana* is a Scythian-Euxine-Irano-Turanian species distributed in Ukraine, Moldavia, Southern Russia, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Middle Asia (Kusnezov, 1927; Dlabola, 1958; 1981; Lodos & Kalkandelen, 1981; Gnezdilov, 2000; Mitjaev, 2002; Demir, 2007; Novikov *et al.*, 2006; Demir & Demirsoy, 2009). The species probably has both bisexual and parthenogenetic populations (Gnezdilov, 2001) and has mostly been known after females (Lodos & Kalkandelen, 1981; Novikov *et al.*, 2006; Demir, 2007; Demir & Demirsoy, 2009). Gnezdilov (2001) described a male from Northwestern Causasus.

References

- Abaii, M.** (2000) *Pests of forest trees and shrubs of Iran*. 178 pp. Ministry of Agriculture, Agricultural Research, Education & Extension Organization.
- Behdad, E.** (1988) *Pests and diseases of forest trees and shrubs and ornamental plants of Iran*. 824 pp. Neshat Publisher, Esfahan.
- Demir, E.** (2007) Auchenorrhyncha (Homoptera) data from Ankara with two new records to Turkey. *Munis Entomology and Zoology* 2(2), 481-492.
- Demir, E. & Demirsoy, A.** (2009) Preliminary report on the Fulgoromorpha (Hemiptera) fauna of Kemalije (Erzincan) with a new record for Turkey. *Munis Entomology and Zoology* 4(1), 280-286.
- Dlabola, J.** (1958) Zikaden-ausbeute vom Kaukasus (Homoptera Auchenorrhyncha). *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* 32, 317-352.
- Dlabola, J.** (1971) Taxonomische und Chorologische erganzungen der zikadenfauna von Anatolian, Iran, Afghanistan und Pakistan (Homoptera: Auchenorrhyncha). *Acta Entomologica Bohemoslovaca, Separatum* 68(6), 377-396.
- Dlabola, J.** (1974) Ergebnisse der Tschechoslowakisch - Iranischen Entomologischen expedition nach dem Iran, 1970, No. 3 (Homoptea: Auchenorrhyncha) (1 Teil). *Acta Entomologica Musei National Pragae, Supplementary* 6, 29-73.
- Dlabola, J.** (1980) Tribus - Einteilung, neue gattungen und arten der subf. Issinae in der eremischen zone (Homoptera, Auchenorrhyncha). *Acta Musei Nationalis Pragae* 47(4), 173-245.

- Dlabola, J.** (1981) Ergebnisse der tschechoslovakisch - Iranische entomologischen expeditionen nach dem Iran 1970 und 1973 (Homoptera: Auchenorrhyncha), II Teil. *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* 40, 127-311.
- Dlabola, J.** (1982) Fortsetzung der Ergänzungen zur Issiden - Taxonomie von Anatolien, Iran und Griechenland (Homoptera: Auchenorrhyncha). *Acta Musei Nationalis Pragae* 38 B(3), 113-169.
- Emeljanov, A. F.** (1974) Proposals on the classification and nomenclature of areals. *Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie* 53(3), 497-522. [English translation published in *Entomological Review* 53(3), 11-26].
- Gnezdilov, V. M.** (2000) To the knowledge of the faunistic complexes of the Cicadina (Homoptera) in the main plant formations of the Northwestern Caucasus. *Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie* 79(4), 794-811. [English translation published in *Entomological Review* 80(8), 927-945].
- Gnezdilov, V. M.** (2001) Notes on *Scorlupella montana* (Becker) (Homoptera: Issidae). *Zoosystematica Rossica* 9, 365-366.
- Kusnezov, V.** (1927) Beitrag zur Kenntnis der armenischen Homopterenfauna. *Zoologischer Anzeiger* 72(9/10), 255-261.
- Lodos, N. & Kalkandelen, A.** (1981) Preliminary list of Auchenorrhyncha with notes on distribution and importance of species in Turkey, IV. Family Issidae Spinola. *Türkiye Bitki Koruma Dergisi* 5(1), 5-21.
- Mirzayans, H.** (1995): *Insects of Iran, the list of Homoptera: Auchenorrhyncha in the Insect Collection of Plant Pests & Diseases Research Institute*. 63 pp. Ministry of Agriculture, Agricultural Research, Education & Extension Organization.
- Mitjaev, I. D.** (2002) Fauna, ecology, and zoogeography of leafhoppers (Homoptera, Cicadinea) of Kazakhstan. *Tethys Entomological Research* 5, 1-171. [In Russian].
- Novikov, D. V., Novikova, N. V., Anufriev, G. A. & Dietrich, Ch. H.** (2006) Auchenorrhyncha (Homoptera) of Kyrgyz Grasslands. *Russian Entomological Journal* 15(3), 303-310.

Received: 7 June 2009

Accepted: 27 October 2009